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Equal Opportunity Within the Workplace

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Abstract

In the recent years, the representation of Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME+) in top management positions has been stagnant despite the increased talent pool. With the current issues arising involving the BAME+ community, it is of no surprise that these ethnic groups are still discriminated, even at their workplace. This is usually due to the culture and type of leadership at the company. Thus, this secondary research paper aims to find out the hurdles culture and leadership climate pose to talented BAME+ employees' career progression. Nonetheless, the investigation, using existing data in the form of surveys, reports, and articles, will be limited to certain companies in the UK and US only. The result of this paper indicates that although there are some companies with good cultures and leaders which allow its BAME+ employees to progress in their careers, most companies do not practice an inclusive culture thus, talented BAME+ staff is often side-lined.

Keywords: Culture, Leadership Climate, BAME+, Career Progression, Ethnic Discrimination

1. Introduction

As of late, the world has seen an unparalleled improvement in workforce compositions due to the increased involvement of Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME+) individuals in the labour force. Although the proportion of BAME+ staff may vary significantly amongst different institutions, their confinement to lower-level positions is almost certain (Wyatt and Silvester, 2015; Roberts and Mayo, 2019). The general perception would be that employees' talent and determination play a huge role in the opportunities received to climb the corporate ladder. However, there is no denying the impact that leaders have on the decision-making processes regarding the selection of talented employees that are deemed fit to develop and progress in their careers (Bean, 2017). Thus, the objective of this paper is to evaluate and discuss the possibilities of culture and climate being the causes that act as hindrance to the career progression of BAME+ staff in a firm and provide recommendations on ways companies can create equal opportunities for the development and progression of their BAME+ staff.

This paper will be divided into four parts which will thus include the literature review, discussion, conclusion as well as the recommendations. Since there is a wide scope relating to the organizations in which BAME+ staff work in, this paper will therefore focus on the cultural and leadership climate barriers which hinder the progression of talented BAME+ staff in certain UK and US companies. Thus, for the purpose of this research paper, more emphasis will be placed on organizational cultures as well as leadership climate. Fakhar et al. (2012) relate

organizational culture to a set of similar values, beliefs and behaviours of employees which can be distinguished by categorizing culture into four different types – clan, adhocracy, market, and hierarchy (Grensing-Pophal, 2018). On the other hand, leadership climate can be defined as the similar perspectives through which leadership in a company is enacted (Day, Griffin and Kim, 2014).

2. Literature Review

As a way of analysing the impact of cultural and leadership climates on the progression of talented BAME+ staff, the literature review of this research paper will touch on five aspects which are Organizational Culture, Leadership Climate, BAME+, Ethnic Discrimination at Workplace and Critical Race Theory.

2.1 Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is often defined as the shared values, viewpoints and beliefs among employees in an organization (Day, Griffin and Kim, 2014; Ostroff, Kinicki and Rabjah, 2013). Fakhar *et al.* (2012) further add that the culture which exists in a workplace is considered strong if majority of the employees adhere to the same beliefs in the organization by choice. In short, a culture which aligns organizational goals to each individual employee's goal is a strong and successful culture that will most probably be able to attract better employees (Maseko, 2017). On the other hand, a weak culture is one whereby majority of the employees in an organization do not share the same beliefs and values (Odor, 2018; Fakhar *et al.*, 2012). Organisational culture, as mentioned by Schein (1990, cited in Odor, 2018), can be demonstrated via three layers, which are, Observable Artefacts, Espoused Values & Beliefs and Basic Underlying Assumptions (Kumar, 2016; Lim, 2019) [*refer to Appendix 1*].

2.1.1 Attributes of Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is better understood by identifying its characteristics and attributes since there is no certain definition for this term. The most common attribute of organizational culture is that it is shared. This is since most of the definitions of culture mention that all the aspects which make up the culture of a company, are shared (Odor, 2018). This attribute is in line with clan culture whereby a lot of similarity exists among employees (Grensing-Pophal, 2018).

To add on, organizational culture, according to Ehrhart, Schneider and Macey (2013), is symbolic, expressive, and subjective. The relationship between culture and symbols is interlinked as culture is made up of different symbols whereas symbols are influenced by cultural practices (Ostroff, Kinicki and Rabiah, 2013; Sigdel, 2018). Culture, such as the adhocracy type, is said to be expressive as it allows individuals to convey their thoughts and emotions (Felipe, Roldan and Leal-Rodriguez, 2017). Nonetheless, symbols and expressions are subjective as they might not have the same contextual meanings when compared with one another (Sigdel, 2018).

Culture is often created by taking into consideration a company's traditions and history. This is supported by Ehrhart, Schneider and Macey (2013) who believe that a company's culture reflects its past as the practices at a workplace are influenced by historical activities. This is linked to another attribution which states that culture provides order and rules to an organization. This is because the shared knowledge regarding certain matters that employees have, creates an order in the workplace that is to be complied with, thereby eliminating ambiguities (Tianya, 2015). The hierarchy and market culture type, as noted by Chandler, Heidrich and Kasa (2017), can be explained using this cultural attribute.

2.2 Leadership Climate

Leadership climate refers to the shared processes, perceptions and procedures regarding policies by means of which leadership is enacted (Day, Griffin and Kim, 2014; Bitsani, 2013). Since meaning is said to be attached to the leader-related perceptions with regards to climate, it is safe to assume that individual members of an organization are subject to the same leadership environment. As noted by Ostroff, Kinicki and Rabiah (2018), climate influences the perception of an employee towards its organization due to the company's practices which

will then affect the employee as well as firm's performances (Dulay, Cakmak, Karadağ, 2015; Nansi *et al.*, 2019). Holloway (2012) believes that since leadership is a two-way relationship between leaders and employees, an appropriate conduct of organizational climate is required to influence employees' behaviour and perceptions.

2.2.1 Dimensions of Organizational Climate

The way leadership climate works in an organization can be explained via the study of organizational climate. According to Day, Griffin and Kim (2014), organizational climate explains the method in which the shared perception of leadership climate affects the outcomes in a company. This is supported by Holloway (2012) who identified three main dimensions of organizational climate, which are **structure**, **responsibility**, and **reward**. **Structure** is the basis on which employees perceive if the policies in a company are well defined. The methods that leaders use to play out their company's strategies to achieve their organizational goals indicate the structure that exists in the company.

To add on, **responsibility**, which requires for both leaders and employees to take charge, depending on the situation. While a leader is responsible to support the development of its employees, employees should also be held responsible with regards to taking up any opportunities available to progress in their career. Another dimension of organizational climate is **reward**, which is what an employee gets for doing a good job. Employees usually look for positive rewards such as pay increments and promotions although the general requirement is for an organization to have a fair reward system within the organization to indicate fairness and equality (Holloway, 2012).

2.3 Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic

Barrett (2018) notes that BAME+ is a well-known term in UK which is used in reference to black, Asian and other minority ethnic individuals who have faced racism due to the colour of their skin tone. However, the ethnic grouping that resulted from using this term when highlighting the inequality and discrimination faced has led to people losing their sense of individuality. Nora and Macaulay (2020) are of the opinion that the term 'BAME,' despite being used officially by the government, should be scraped off as it marginalizes non-white individuals and puts them into one category despite the difference in issues and challenges faced by each and every ethnic group.

2.3.1 Labyrinth Theory

Wyatt and Silvester (2015) came up with a theory of linking the challenges faced by the BAME employees in the workplace with 'Labyrinth,' a metaphor relating to an elaborate maze which has its prize in the centre. Nonetheless, since there are various routes that lead up to the centre, the experience of each individual while navigating the maze will most certainly be different. The 'glass ceiling' term that is frequently used to describe the challenges faced by women in comparison to men, was used as a reference by Wyatt and Silvester (2015) as they argue that BAME employees face a 'concrete ceiling' scenario since the hurdles they have to overcome in order to climb the corporate ladder are more challenging and difficult. This explains why although more organizations have increased their recruitment rates of BAME individuals, only a few of these BAME employees manage to attain senior level or leadership roles (Budjanovcanin, 2015).

2.4 Ethnic Discrimination at Workplace

Discrimination at a workplace often indicates inequality among certain minoritized groups in comparison to others (Triana, Jayasinghe and Pieper, 2015). The difference in treatment includes, but is not limited to recruitment, remuneration and lack of opportunities to develop one's career. These three aspects, as noted by Budjanovcanin (2015), are inharmonious because although one might get recruited, the employment will not provide assurance that the employee will be given an appropriate remuneration or trainings and promotions in order to develop and progress in their career. This explains why minority groups usually have lower-level jobs, with close to no opportunity for advancement (Wyatt and Silvester, 2015).

2.4.1 Types of Discrimination

Discrimination, previously, used to be blatant and in an overt form. However, due to the recent political changes with regards to minoritized ethnic groups, discrimination has taken a more covert form, as people now display their prejudice and racism in a subtle way (Williams, 2015). Ethnic discrimination often refers to racial discrimination involving those from minority ethnics. Although not apparent as before, discrimination, any and all types of it, still exists. The recent form of racial discrimination is known as **modern racism** as there is a preconceived notion that because minoritized individuals are now getting opportunities to pursue their careers, they are no longer discriminated (Roberts and Mayo, 2019).

Modern racism can be explained through **microaggression, colour-blind perspective** as well as **tokenism**. **Microaggression**, as Williams (2015) notes, is a term used to describe the discrimination faced mostly by racial and ethnic minorities, which often goes unnoticed by others. Microaggression has elements of overt as well as covert forms as two of its subcategories, microinsult and microinvalidation, refer to subtly insulting and invalidating an individual's competency and struggles (Harrison and Tanner, 2018) whereas microassault refers to the blatant use of derogatory terms to target and verbally attack minoritized individuals.

In addition to that is the **colour-blind perspective** that most organizations adopt to indicate that all individuals are viewed the same despite their apparent differences. This refers to another covert form of discrimination as those who hold this view are less likely to be aware of their discriminatory actions. The concept of this perspective which is to convince people that everyone is treated the same invalidates the discrimination faced by others (Williams, 2015). **Tokenism**, on the other hand, is when companies hire certain individuals for the sole purpose of avoiding criticism. In this context, tokenism is the act of recruiting individuals from minority ethnics to display the firm as fair and inclusive (Yilmaz and Dalkilic, 2019).

2.4.2 Factors of Discrimination

Ethnic discrimination occurs either deliberately or unconsciously as racism has been inhabited and inherited in everyday life. Salter, Adams and Perez (2018) believe that using the cultural-psychological perspective to understand racism allows for ethnic discrimination to be understood. One of the main factors of discrimination is the feeling of **superiority** that exists in certain individuals whereby they assume their characteristics, most noticeably, their skin tone, makes their ethnic group seem more developed than those different from them. For instance, '**white superiority**' is a term that has been widely used in the recent years due to the privileges that white individuals, be it at their workplace or in general, get since they have lighter skin tones (Gray, 2019).

Another factor that causes ethnic discrimination at a workplace is **homophily**, which Wyatt and Silvester (2015) explained to be the tendency of employees to form links with those who are ethnically similar. Thus, in this context, there is inequality among the groups that exist at a workplace as those belonging in majority ethnic groups more often than not hold a powerful position and the forming of network with employees who have similar characteristics will result in the ethnically minoritized employees being left out from important social networking activities (Lawrence and Shah, 2020).

2.5 Critical Race Theory

Critical Race Theory (CRT) touches upon issues regarding inequality and discrimination and demands for radical change in organizations and systems as a way of reducing the discrimination faced by minoritized ethnics (Campbell, 2014). CRT attempts to challenge the notion that 'Whites' are the standards by being more inclusive towards the other ethnic groups. The six main tenets of CRT [*refer to Appendix 2*], as identified by Rocco, Bernier and Bowman (2014) touch upon society's regularization of classifying citizens by their race and essential identity, which, as supported by De La Garza and Ono (2016), can be restrained if minoritized ethnic individuals were given opportunities to share their perspectives, thereby validating their struggles and experience.

3. Discussion

Odor (2018) is of the opinion that culture plays a big part in motivating and shaping the performance of its' employees which will ultimately have an impact on the performance of the organization (Maseko, 2017). Organizational culture, as agreed by Edwinah and Mildred (2013), should be measured based on its effectiveness instead of the benefits a certain type of culture will have on the company and its employees. Thus, no matter if a company practices clan, market, adhocracy, or hierarchy culture, if the leaders of the company do not ensure the culture and working environment is suitable for its employees, the organizational culture will not be effective in bringing out the best in its employees. To add on, Seppala and Cameron (2015) believe that **positive leadership climate**, where leaders ensure all employees are treated well and are presented with opportunities fairly, also contributes to creating a positive workplace culture as leaders play a huge role in motivating employees (Nansi et al., 2019; Fang et al., 2019). Thus, it is important for companies to focus on cultures that are beneficial to their organization whilst taking up measures to put an end to the beliefs and practices at the workplace that do not provide any positive result (Odor, 2018).

A biased leadership climate at the workplace will result in unfair treatment amongst employees whereby one group will be given all the chances while another group will be deprived of deserving opportunities. Although as of late companies have made it their aim to promote diversity and be more inclusive, the methods adopted by these firms have not resulted in any proper changes as BAME+ employees rarely receive opportunities to acquire top level positions due to organizational culture and leadership climate (Roberts and Mayo, 2019). This is supported by a **survey** conducted by the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (2017) through YouGov PLC involving 1290 UK employees which showed that 38% BAME employees felt that their career progression did not meet their expectations and most of the reasons cited were office politics, working practices or culture, disregard of an individual's talent as well as the lack of training and development programs. Although 57% of the BAME employees agree to have an inclusive corporate culture at their workplace, about 34% of them feel the need to tweak their behaviour to fit in with the rest of the employees at work [*refer to Appendix 3*].

Many companies now project themselves as ethnically inclusive although the corporate culture and actions of these companies indicate that the recruitment of BAME+ staff is done out of political correctness to avoid being questioned by the public (Foote, 2018; Abril, 2020). Thus, these companies hire BAME+ staff for the sake of it instead of allowing the employees to develop their skills and progress in their respective careers. For instance, **Bon Appetit**, a food magazine channel on YouTube, was called out by its ex-employees for not approving ideas by its BAME+ employees while presenting the business as one that cares about minoritized ethnics (Harris, Haasch and Greenspan, 2020). This shows that companies, despite hiring BAME+ staff, prefer to focus on the career progression of their white employees whilst treating their BAME+ staff as tokens for brownie points from the public instead of creating a fair culture at the workplace which favors all the employees equally (O'Keefe, 2020). Unsurprisingly, a similar situation transpired at **Refinery29**, a media and entertainment company, where the co-founder of the company was accused of rejecting work involving BAME+ individuals citing absurd reasons (Flynn, 2020). This shows that modern racism inadvertently exists in the culture of many companies despite firms indicating the opposite.

Poor culture at companies like **Google**, which is said to be tolerant towards racism and sexism (Levin, 2017) also affects the career progression of talented BAME+ staffs due to the discouraging and discriminative, especially microaggressive behavior at their workplace thereby resulting in employees leaving the firm as they are neither respected nor presented with opportunities that will help them progress in their careers (Guynn, 2020). Despite being termed as the exemplar of clan culture in a company, most BAME+ employees at Google have raised their voice regarding the favoritism (Abril, 2020) that goes on in Google whereby white male managers, the dominant group in the company, only supports and promotes those similar to themselves. This can be linked to the sociological theory, **homophily**, as noted by Wyatt and Silvester (2015), whereby the white men at Google often create social networks amongst themselves which then allows them to receive more advanced opportunities whereas the talented BAME+ staffs are excluded and reduced to low level jobs since they do not have role models who can lead and guide them (Levin, 2017).

Despite the increased need for diversity and inclusion at the workplace to combat racism and provide BAME+ individuals a safe space to carry on with their jobs and showcase their talents, certain companies are still ambivalent about giving opportunities to BAME+ employees to progress in their careers. Much of this could be linked to the type of culture a company has adopted at their workplace which normalizes homophily and the need to remain in power and be seen as superior (Rocco, Bernier and Bowman, 2014; Ray, 2019; Wingfield and Chavez, 2020). The **British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC)**, with its top-down leadership style which indicates hierarchy type culture at the firm, is one example of top management refusing any change as the only BAME+ board member of the company was removed (Roberts, 2021). The removal of the senior BAME+ member, against the diversity guidelines of the firm (British Broadcasting Corporation, 2018), has left the BBC News Board homogenous. This shows that leaders and the top management are more responsible than projected with regards to the development of BAME+ staff thereby justifying the claim that culture and leadership climate are barriers to the progression of talented BAME+ employees.

On the contrary, there are companies in UK and US that practice good corporate culture and leadership climate as well. This shows that responsible companies still exist as the management and leaders of these companies are aware of the prevailing inherent differences, in line with the **Critical Race Theory**, among employees of diverse ethnicities at a workplace, instead of adopting a colour-blind perspective which will make BAME+ employees feel invalidated (Rocco, Bernier and Bowman, 2014; De La Garza and Ono, 2016). These companies do not only work on creating an environment and culture that is inclusive of all, no matter the race or ethnicity but the leaders are also empathetic and mindful of the consequences of their behaviour and actions on the firm as well as the employees. Thus, companies with good cultures and supportive leaders often pave the way for talented BAME+ staff to receive training and promotions which helps the employees progress in their careers (Seppala and Cameron, 2015).

One such firm that supports and cares for its BAME+ staff is **Sainsbury's**, a supermarket chain in the UK. The Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of Sainsbury's, Mike Coupe, has created an extremely inclusive culture at the workplace, despite public backlash (Skopeliti, 2020; Mamona, 2020, Gayle, 2020), which encourages employees to be more participative. Inclusion in this context not only refers to BAME+ staff feeling included in the workplace but also refers to the involvement of leaders in the daily work life of these employees (Carayol, 2021). Leaders that are constantly involved in the employees' work can monitor their progress and recommend training programmes that will benefit the employee and indirectly, the company as well (Fang *et al.*, 2019). One of the dimensions of organization climate, which is responsibility, requires for employees to be responsible for their own careers and to take up all opportunities presented to them (Holloway, 2012). Thus, in an inclusive culture, as observed in Sainsbury's, communication between employees and leaders is made easier and the interdependence amongst both parties will result in a trusting relationship as well.

Another company with good culture and leadership climate which benefits BAME+ staff is **Accenture**, a professional service firm which is included in the Top 10 Diversity and Inclusion Index (Pratt, 2020). Accenture's achievement in receiving this accolade consecutively (Cole, 2019) indicates that the firm is not just making empty promises to the public but is instead taking up serious measures to achieve its mission of "improving the way the world works" (Jesiah and Kalakada, 2013, p. 6) as the firm has managed to create a good and inclusive culture which allows all its employees, regardless of their race and ethnic, to prosper in their respective careers (Sweet and Shook, 2020). Accenture's secret to success in creating an equal and inclusive culture should be credited to their leaders who believe in treating each employee as an individual first instead of categorizing them as per minority groups (Bell, 2018).

Although **Sainsbury's and Accenture** support the narrative against organizational culture and leadership climate being barriers to the career progression of talented BAME+ staff, it is not enough to completely disregard the claim. This is because out of the innumerable companies that exist in UK and US, only a selected few walk the talk and provide opportunities for the development of BAME+ staff at their workplace. Even then, BAME+ staff are not treated equally as one ethnic group often gets an advantage over the other. For instance, **Intel's** numbers regarding race, pay and gender equality showed that Asians were dominating the firm's top ranks (Musil, 2019; Ingram, 2019; Green and Recht, 2019) but the number of other minorities, such as African Americans and

Hispanics do not even sum up to half the number of Asians [*refer to Appendix 4*] (Intel, 2020). This indicates unequal treatment of BAME+ employees at workplace which reaffirms the claim of cultural and leadership climates as barriers.

4. Conclusion

To conclude, the career progression of talented BAME+ staff differs from one another, but the main barriers faced to advance in their respective careers can be classified into two – **organizational culture** and **leadership climate**. Although the scope of this study is extended to certain companies in the United Kingdom and United States of America only, there is no doubt that these barriers hinder the career development of BAME+ employees in other countries as well since racial inequality still exists (Drew, 2021) in various nations. Racial inequality results in unconscious bias and favouritism, among other forms of discrimination, and thus, it plays a part in the type of culture that is created at a workplace by the leaders (Roberts et al., 2020). Since this paper used a secondary research method, a further research can be done by conducting surveys in specific companies to find out if internalised racism affects the career progression of ethnically minoritized individuals in their own countries.

5. Recommendations

One of the ways companies can create equal opportunity for talent development and progression within the workplace is by **changing the corporate culture** (McGregor-Smith, 2017). As discussed before, certain companies with an unjust culture do not allow for their BAME+ employees to advance in their career thus it is important for organizations to change their ways and understand why inclusion and diversity are important for their business. As Day, Griffin and Kim (2014) have noted, variation is vital to promote diversity as it benefits the company since competitive advantage among employees brings out the best in them (Urbancova, Hudakova and Fajcikova, 2020). In fact, employees from different ethnicities have different and unique perspectives which can contribute to the success of the firm (Matthews, 2017; Scarborough, Lambouths and Holbrook, 2019). Thus, the first step towards creating equal opportunities is to create an inclusive culture at the workplace.

In addition to that, companies can **introduce leadership programmes** in order to provide training to their leaders regarding unconscious biasness (Ashe and Nazroo, 2015; McGregor-Smith, 2017) and subsequently monitor the change in behaviour of these leaders in their interactions with BAME+ employees (Williams, 2015). By implementing this programme, companies can also allocate and achieve new talent development and progression targets in accordance with their diversity and inclusion strategies while leaders can devise individual development plans for each employee (Roberts and Mayo, 2019). The management of **Ernst and Young (EY)** has initiated a similar Inclusive Leadership Programme (ILP) at their workplace (McGregor-Smith, 2017) which has resulted in a remarkable number of BAME+ employee promotions in 2019 (Smith, 2020) thereby motivating the company to invest in similar programmes.

Lastly, companies should **set fixed policies regarding recruitment, training, and promotion** of all their employees and strictly adhere to these regulations without letting any biasness cloud their judgment (Kang et al., 2016) as a way to avoid discrimination amongst employees. For instance, leaders or those in charge of suggesting promotion or training programmes should monitor the performance of their employees using fixed guidelines or indicators (Ali, Sofia and Kalsom, 2019) instead of making the decision on one's adequacy to receive any promotion or training that will develop and advance their careers based on their race or ethnicity (Wang and Seifert, 2018). Thus, this will allow all employees to receive equal opportunities based on their merits and BAME+ employees will not have to change themselves (Kang et al., 2016; Roberts and Mayo, 2019) to fit in with the rest in order to make themselves eligible for training and promotions.

References

- Abril, D. (2020) *Facebook and Google preach racial equality. But they lack it on their leadership teams*. Available at: <https://fortune.com/2020/06/08/facebook-google-racial-equity-inequity-donations-culture-leadership/> (Accessed: 1 April 2021).
- Ali Ahmed Ateeq Ali, Sofia Hayati Yusoff and Kalsom Ali (2019) 'Fundamental of Equal Opportunities in Employee's Performance: A Critical Review,' 5th World Conference on Integration of Knowledge, 29 July. Bangi: World Conference Resources.
- Ashe, S. D. and Nazroo, J. (2015) *Equality, Diversity and Racism in the Workplace: A Qualitative Analysis of the 2015 Race at Work Survey*. Manchester: Centre on Dynamics of Ethnicity.
- Barrett, G. (2018) *Why Its Time to Ditch the Term 'BAME'*. Available at: <https://www.refinery29.com/en-gb/2018/05/199526/what-does-bame-stand-for> (Accessed: 29 March 2021).
- British Broadcasting Corporation (2018) *Reflecting the Ethnic Diversity of The UK Within the BBC Workforce*. London: British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) Books.
- Bean, S. (2017) *Over a quarter of black employees say racial discrimination hinders careers*. Available at: <https://www.workplaceinsight.net/over-a-quarter-of-black-employees-say-racial-discrimination-hinders-career/> (Accessed: 19 February 2021).
- Bell, A. (2018) *Intersectionality: look at the individual, not the minority group*. Available at: <https://www.ft.com/content/331bf3a0-1d48-11e8-a748-5da7d696ccab> (Accessed: 14 April 2021).
- Bitsani, E. (2013) 'Theoretical Approaches to the Organizational Culture and Climate: Exploratory Research Examples and Best Policies in Health Care Services', *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 1(4), pp. 48 – 58.
- Budjanovcanin, A. (2015) 'Ethnic Discrimination', in Cooper, C. L., Guest, D. E. and Needle, D. J. (eds.) *Wiley Encyclopedia of Management*. Chichester: Wiley, pp. 85 – 87.
- Campbell, E. (2014) 'Using Critical Race Theory to Measure Racial Competency among Social Workers', *Journal of Sociology and Social Work*, 2(2), pp. 73 – 86. doi: 10.15640/jssw.v2n2a5.
- Carayol, R. (2021) *Diversity is a fact – inclusion is a choice*. Available at: managementtoday.co.uk/diversity-fact-inclusion-choice/leadership-lessons/article/1708460 (Accessed: 13 April 2021).
- Chandler, N., Heidrich, B. and Kasa, R. (2017) 'A longitudinal study of market-oriented subcultures in higher education', *Forum on Economics and Business*, 20(133), pp. 3 – 10.
- Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (2017) *Addressing the barriers to BAME employee career progression to the top*. London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development Publishing.
- Cole, C. (2019) *Accenture tops Refinitiv Index of World's most diverse and inclusive companies*. Available at: <https://www.diversityq.com/accenture-tops-refinitiv-index-of-worlds-most-diverse-and-inclusive-companies-1507716/> (Accessed: 14 April 2021).
- Day, D. V., Griffin, M. A. and Kim, R. L. (2014) 'The Climate and Culture of Leadership in Organizations' in Schneider, B. and Barbera, K. M. (eds.) *The Oxford Handbook of Organizational Climate and Culture*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 104 – 117.
- De La Garza, A. T. and Ono, K. A. (2016) 'Critical Race Theory', in Jensen, K. B., Rothenbuhler, E. W., Pooley, J. D. and Craig, R. T. (eds.) *The International Encyclopedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy*. Chichester: Wiley, pp. 391 – 397.
- Drew, K. (2021) *10 Worst Countries for Racial Equality, Ranked by Perception*. Available at: <https://www.usnews.com/news/best-countries/slideshows/worst-countries-for-racial-equality?slide=12> (Accessed: 17 April 2021).
- Dulay, S. I., Çakmak, E. and Karadağ, E. (2015) 'The Effect of Leadership on Organizational Climate', in Karadağ, E. (ed.) *Leadership and Organizational Outcomes*. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, pp. 123 – 141.
- Edwinah, A. and Mildred, D. W. (2013) 'Corporate Culture: A Tool for Control and Effectiveness in Organizations', *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(15), pp. 42 – 44.
- Ehrhart, M. G., Schneider, B. and Macey, W. H. (2013) *Organizational Climate and Culture: An Introduction to Theory, Research and Practice*. London: Routledge.
- Fakhar Shahzad, Rana Adeel Luqman, Ayesha Rashid Khan and Lalarukh Shabbir (2012) 'Impact of Organizational Culture on Organizational Performance: An Overview', *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3(9), pp. 975 – 985.
- Fang, Y. C., Chen, J. Y., Wang, M. J. and Chen, C. Y. (2019) 'The Impact of Inclusive Leadership on Employees' Innovative Behaviors: The Mediation of Psychological Capital', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, pp. 1 – 4.
- Felipe, C. M., Roldan, J. L. and Leal-Rodriguez, A. L. (2017) 'Impact of Organizational Culture Values on Organizational Agility', *Sustainability*, 9(12), pp. 2 – 7.

- Flynn, K. (2020) *Refinery29 is reeling from claims of racism and toxic work culture*. Available at: <https://www.edition.cnn.com/2020/06/11/media/refinery29-workplace-culture/index.html> (Accessed: 1 April 2021).
- Foote, A. (2018) *Google's Diversity Stats Are Still Very Dismal*. Available at: <https://www.wired.com/story/googles-employee-diversity-numbers-havent-really-improved/> (Accessed: 1 April 2021).
- Gayle, L. (2020) *Customers accuse Sainsbury's of 'virtue signalling' over Christmas advert showing an all-black family and claim the retailer is 'not inclusive'*. Available at: <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/femail/article-8954151/Twitter-call-Sainsburys-boycott-release-Christmas-advert-showing-black-family.html> (Accessed: 14 April 2021).
- Gray, A. (2019) *The Bias of 'Professionalism' Standards*. Available at: https://ssir.org/articles/entry/the_bias_of_professionalism_standards# (Accessed: 31 March 2021).
- Green, J. and Recht, H. (2019) *Intel is first to share detailed pay disparities. It's not flattering*. Available at: <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/features/2019-12-10/intel-s-gender-pay-data-highlights-challenges-in-silicon-valley> (Accessed: 8 April 2021).
- Grenging-Pophal, L. (2018) *4 Distinct Types of Corporate Culture – Which is Yours?* Available at: <https://hrdailyadvisor.blr.com/2018/04/12/4-distinct-types-corporate-culture/> (Accessed: 9 April 2021).
- Guynn, J. (2020) *#SiliconValleySoWhite: Black Facebook and Google employees speak out on big tech racism*. Available at: <https://www.usatoday.com/story/tech/2020/02/10/racial-discrimination-persists-facebook-google-employees-say/4307591002/> (Accessed: 1 April 2021).
- Harris, M., Haasch, P. and Greenspan, R. E. (2020) *Bon Appetit announced 8 new chefs after its YouTube channel devolved into chaos. Here's how the publication ended up in hot water*. Available at: <https://www.insider.com/bon-apptit-timeline-allegations-drama-culture-race-andy-alex-sohla-2020-6> (Accessed: 21 January 2021).
- Harrison, C. and Tanner, K. D. (2018) 'Language Matters: Considering Microaggressions in Science', *CBE – Life Sciences Education*, 17(1), pp. 1 – 8.
- Holloway, J. B. (2012) 'Leadership Behavior and Organizational Climate: An Empirical Study in a Non-profit Organization', *Emerging Leadership Journeys*, 5(1), pp. 9 – 35.
- Ingram, D. (2019) *Intel broke ranks to talk about pay, race and gender. Now other tech companies are getting heat*. Available at: <https://www.nbcnews.com/tech/tech-news/intel-broke-ranks-talk-about-pay-race-gender-now-other-n1101546> (Accessed: 8 April 2021).
- Intel (2020) *Diversity and Inclusion are Key to Innovation*. Available at: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/diversity/diversity-at-intel.html> (Accessed: 14 April 2021).
- Jesiah, S. and Kalakada, U. L. (2013) 'Workforce Diversity at Accenture: A key to Corporate Success', in Gupta, B., Mishra, S. and Routray, S. (eds.) *Resource Book on Case Studies in Business Management*. New Delhi: Ane Books Pvt Lt, pp. 5 – 6.
- Kang, S. K., DeCelles, K. A., Tilcsik, A. and Jun, S. (2016) 'Whitened resumes: race and self-presentation in the labor market', *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 61(3), pp. 469 – 502.
- Kumar, A. (2016) 'Refined and Importance of Organizational Culture', *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: A: Administration and Management*, 16(4), pp. 14 – 18.
- Lawrence, B. S. and Shah, N. P. (2020) 'Homophily: Measures and Meaning', *Academy of Management Annals*, 14(2), pp. 513 – 597.
- Levin, S. (2017) *Women say they quit Google because of racial discrimination: 'I was invisible'*. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2017/aug/18/women-google-memo-racism-sexism-discrimination-quit> (Accessed: 1 April 2021).
- Lim, S. (2019) *Looking at humor in organizational culture*. Available at: awakengroup.com/knowledge-base/looking-at-humor-in-organizational-culture/ (Accessed: 24 March 2021).
- Mamona, S. (2020) *The backlash to the Sainsbury's advert proves the UK *is* still a racist country*. Available at: <https://www.glamourmagazine.co.uk/article/sainsburys-advert-racism> (Accessed: 14 April 2021).
- Maseko, T. S. B. (2017) 'Strong vs. Weak Organizational Culture: Assessing the Impact on Employee Motivation', *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 7(1), pp. 1 – 5. doi: 10.4172/2223-5833.1000287.
- Matthews, V. (2017) *How can organizations support better progression for BAME employees?* Available at: www.personneltoday.com/hr/can-organisations-support-better-progression-bame-employees/ (Accessed: 9 April 2021).
- McGregor-Smith, R. (2017) *Race in the workplace*. London: Luminous Publishing.
- Musil, S. (2019) *Intel offers detailed look into employee pay disparities*. Available at: www.cnet.com/news/intel-offers-detailed-look-into-employee-pay-disparities/ (Accessed: 8 April 2021).
- Nansi Lidya Lolowang, Eka Afnan Troena, Atim Djazuli and Siti Aisjah (2019) 'The Effect of Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance that is Educated by Motivation', *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 17(1), pp. 268 – 277. doi: 10.21511/ppm.17(1).2019.23.

- Nora Fakim and Macaulay, C. (2020) 'Don't call me BAME': Why some people are rejecting the term? Available at: www.bbc.com/news/uk-53194376 (Accessed: 29 March 2021).
- O'Keefe, M. (2020) *Can We Ever Enjoy the Bon Appetit Test Kitchen Videos Again?* Available at: <https://www.decider.com/2020/06/11/bon-appetit-test-kitchen-youtube-racism-scandal-what-next/> (Accessed: 12 April 2021).
- Odor, H. O. (2018) 'Organisational Culture and Dynamics', *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 6(1), pp. 31 – 39.
- Ostroff, C., Kinicki, A. J. and Rabiah Muhammad (2013) 'Organizational Culture and Climate', in Weiner, I. B., Schmitt, N. W. and Highhouse, S. (eds.) *Handbook of Psychology*. New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons, pp. 647 – 648.
- Pratt, L. (2020) *Accenture, Allianz and L'Oreal named best global employers for diversity and inclusion*. Available at: [https://www.employeebenefits.co.uk/most-diverse-inclusive-organisations/#:~:text=Accenture%2C%20Allianz%20and%20L'Oreal,employers%20for%20diversity%20and%20inclusion&text=Accenture%20\(pictured\)%2C%20Blackrock%2C,inclusion%20index%20\(D%26I%20index\)](https://www.employeebenefits.co.uk/most-diverse-inclusive-organisations/#:~:text=Accenture%2C%20Allianz%20and%20L'Oreal,employers%20for%20diversity%20and%20inclusion&text=Accenture%20(pictured)%2C%20Blackrock%2C,inclusion%20index%20(D%26I%20index)) (Accessed: 14 April 2021).
- Ray, V. (2019) *Why So Many Organizations Stay White*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2019/11/why-so-many-organizations-stay-white> (Accessed: 13 April 2021).
- Roberts, L. M. and Mayo, A. J. (2019) *Toward a Racially Just Workplace*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2019/11/toward-a-racially-just-workplace> (Accessed: 28 January 2021).
- Roberts, L. (2021) *Removal of BBC's only BAME board member suggests wider 'ongoing cultural problem', MPs claim*. Available at: www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2021/02/17/removal-bbcs-bame-board-member-suggests-wider-ongoing-cultural/ (Accessed: 8 April 2021).
- Roberts, S. O., Bareket-Shavit, C., Dollins, F. A., Goldie, P. D. and Mortenson, E. (2020) 'Racial Inequality in Psychological Research: Trends of the Past and Recommendations for the Future', *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 15(6), pp. 1303 – 1306.
- Rocco, T. S., Bernier, J. D. and Bowman, L. (2014) 'Critical Race Theory and HRD: Moving Race Front and Center', *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 16(4), pp. 457 – 470.
- Salter, P. S., Adams, G. and Perez, M. J. (2018) 'Racism in the Structure of Everyday Worlds: A Cultural-Psychological Perspective', *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 27(3), pp. 150 – 155. doi: 10.1177/0963721417724239.
- Scarborough, W. J., Lambouths, D. L. and Holbrook, A. L. (2019) 'Support of workplace diversity policies: The role of race, gender, and beliefs about inequality', *Social Science Research*, 79, pp. 197 – 207.
- Seppala, E. and Cameron, K. (2015) *Proof that Positive Work Cultures are More Productive*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2015/12/proof-that-positive-work-cultures-are-more-productive> (Accessed: 14 April 2021).
- Sigdel, S. B. (2018) 'Culture and Symbolism Nexus in Anthropology', *Janapriya Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 7(1), pp. 116 – 124.
- Skopeliti, C. (2020) *UK supermarkets unite after Sainsbury's advert prompts racist backlash*. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/nov/28/uk-supermarkets-unite-after-sainsburys-advert-prompts-racist-backlash> (Accessed: 14 April 2021).
- Smith, P. (2020) *BAME 2020: Zaheer Ahmad, head of strategic delivery, EY*. Available at: <https://www.accountancydaily.co/bame-2020-zaheer-ahmad-head-strategic-delivery-ey> (Accessed: 10 April 2021).
- Sweet, J. and Shook, E. (2020) *Getting to Equal 2020*. Dublin: Accenture Plc.
- Tianya, L. L. (2015) *Organization Culture and Employee Behaviour: Case Study*. Lahti University of Applied Sciences. Available at: https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/92815/LI_Tianya.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y (Accessed: 27 March 2021).
- Triana, M. C., Jayasinghe, M. and Pieper, J. R. (2015) 'Perceived workplace racial discrimination and its correlates: A meta-analysis', *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 36(4), pp. 491 – 513.
- Urbancova, H., Hudakova, M. and Fajcikova, A. (2020) 'Diversity Management as a Tool of Sustainability of Competitive Advantage', *Sustainability*, 12(12), pp. 1 – 6. doi:10.3390/su12125020.
- Wang, W. and Seifert, R. (2018) 'BAME Staff and Public Service Motivation: The Mediating Role of Perceived Fairness in English Local Government', *Journal of Business Ethics*, 161(3), pp. 653 – 664.
- Williams, A. (2015) 'Modern-day racism in the workplace: Symbolic diversity or real change?', *From Science to Practice: Organizational Psychology Bulletin*, 1(1), pp. 6 – 10.
- Wingfield, A. H. and Chavez, K. (2020) 'Getting In, Getting Hired, Getting Sideways Looks: Organizational Hierarchy and Perceptions of Racial Discrimination', *American Sociological Review*, 85(1), pp. 31 – 36.
- Wyatt, M. and Silvester, J. (2015) 'Reflections on the labyrinth: Investigating black and minority ethnic leaders' career experiences', *Human Relations*, 68(8), pp. 1243 – 1269.
- Yilmaz, B. K. and Dalkilic, O. S. (2019) 'Conceptual Framework About Tokenism Phenomenon in Organizations', *International Journal of Contemporary Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 9(2), pp. 205 – 231.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Layers of Organizational Culture (Lim, 2019)

Appendix 2: Tenets of Critical Race Theory (Rocco, Bernier and Bowman, 2014)

Appendix 3: Survey Results involving 1290 UK employees (Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development, 2017)

Table 6: Which, if any, of the following factors RELATED TO THE WORKPLACE have prevented you from meeting your career expectations? (% of those who said their career progression to date has failed to meet expectations) (Respondents were asked to select UP TO FIVE factors that have been most significant)

	Net: BAME	Indian/ Bangladeshi/ Pakistani	Chinese/other Asian	Black	Mixed race	Other ethnic group	White British
Base	258	72	34	47	63	42	184
My skills and talent have been overlooked	35	35	31	27	46	28	31
Negative office politics	31	32	24	32	33	29	29
A lack of effective training and development programmes at work	30	20	42	30	31	40	26
Experienced poor quality line management from my immediate manager when I entered work or at key points during my career	29	26	45	25	28	28	35
Job vacancies at higher levels than my current role don't become vacant very often	30	25	30	31	37	20	34
Engrained working practices or cultures have made it hard to progress	27	18	37	32	27	18	26
Poor performance management at work has meant my achievements are not recognised	19	12	31	16	19	30	30
Received no training or inadequate training when I first entered the workplace	19	13	12	21	25	19	17
Experienced discrimination (that is, related to age, disability, gender, gender reassignment, race, religion/belief or sexual orientation)	20	22	9	29	15	17	11
A lack of flexible working opportunities	18	16	20	24	16	7	14
Did not benefit from a coach or mentor when entering employment or at key points in my career	16	12	21	17	17	14	13
Lack of role models in my organisation of 'people like me' with a similar identity or background	17	20	17	19	11	19	11
Was not able to get on an effective graduate programme after completing a degree	12	13	5	9	16	17	3
Was not able to get on an effective apprenticeship programme	3	2	0	3	6	3	2

Figure 9: My organisation has an inclusive culture (% agree)

Base: BAME: 700; Asian: 116

Figure 11: I feel I need to change aspects of my behaviour at work in order to fit in (% agree)

Base: Indian/Pakistani/Bangladeshi: 201; Chinese/other Asian 117; black: 111; mixed race: 155; other ethnic group: 116; BAME: 700; white British: 590.

Appendix 4: Intel's Overall Employees and Executive Data (Intel, 2020)

